

maximum yield gain obtained during the WS derived from the performance of hybrids vs Jaya was 544 kg ha⁻¹ in 1991 and 1,522 kg ha⁻¹ in 1995. Similarly, in DS, the yield gain in hybrid rice was 846 kg ha⁻¹ in 1991-92 and 1,634 kg ha⁻¹ in 1993-94. The heterosis for grain yield increased—from 14% (1991) to 31% (1995) in the WS, and from 8% (1991-92) to 27% (1993-94) in the DS. The results indicate that hybrids undoubtedly have a yield advantage over high-yielding varieties such as Jaya. The margin of yield gain increased over the years. The diversity of material added over time may be the reason for such gains. The hybrids are also as widely adaptable as Jaya. ■

Yield stability in rice hybrids

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Hybrid rice technology is considered to have the most potential and be readily exploitable to further raise the yield ceiling in the irrigated ecosystem. But successful exploitation over a large area depends on identifying stable hybrids. Yield heterosis is reported to be a variable trait, which depends not only on parent combinations but also on environmental conditions. Stability for yield of rice hybrids is therefore analyzed. We examined the stability of hybrids for yield in two sets of environments categorized as low and high. Grain yield data of 10 trials conducted between the 1994 wet season (WS) and 1995 WS were used. Locations with a mean yield lower than the grand mean yield were termed low environments, whereas those with a mean yield higher than the grand mean yield were identified as high environments. We analyzed grain yield data on eight hybrids in the 1994-95 WS and dry season tested along with inbred Jaya, Rasi, and IR36 at five locations. The mean yield and coefficient of variation over

seasons and locations were calculated for both hybrids and inbreds to find environment-dependent heterosis.

The mean grain yield advantage of the best-yielding hybrid over Jaya was calculated for each environment. The results indicated that the stability of rice hybrids for grain yield is comparable with that of the best inbred check variety, Jaya. Some of the hybrids, such as IR58025A / IR34686 and IR58025A / IR29723, showed better yield stability over seasons compared with Jaya. But the yield heterosis of the hybrids was better expressed in environments categorized as high. ■

Exploiting heterosis using TGMS lines in intra- and intersubspecific hybridization

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The performance of various thermo-sensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines was assessed in order to use them in two-line intra- and intersubspecific hybridization with wide compatibility lines. Some 26 lines comprising TGMS lines, indica accessions, and japonica with wide compatibility (WC) gene(s) were used to make 65 hybrids: 31 were indica / indica and 34 were indica / japonica (WC). Standard heterosis was recorded up to 58%. Seed yield (g plant⁻¹) ranged from 2.3 to 31.3. The number of heterotic combinations was higher in intersubspecific cross combinations. Spikelet fertility ranged from 2.7 to 88.4% in intersubspecific crosses and from 3.6 to 96.0% in intrasubspecific crosses. The WC lines were not universally compatible in all combinations. The TGMS line ID / 24 was completely

compatible with all WC as well as with other indica accessions.

A molecular phylogenetic map was constructed involving all 26 lines based on the polymorphism generated by 10 random primers—OPD3, OPU7, OPU14, OPZ18, OPZ19, OPZ20, OPA7 + OPA6, and OPA12 + OPD5. By using the un-weighted pair-group method, arithmetic average (UPGMA), a dendrogram was made, taking into consideration the distance calculated based on Jaccard similarity indices. The genetic distances were from 0.2 to 0.88. The height in hybrids increased as the genetic distance between the parents widened. With genetic distance > 0.70 among parents, spikelet fertility and grain yield plant⁻¹ decreased considerably. Heterotic combinations were observed when the genetic distance ranged from 0.4 to 0.7 among parents. ■

Developing CMS and restorer lines of tropical rice hybrids

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The successful development and cultivation of hybrid rice in China in 1976 encouraged IRRI scientists and collaborating countries to intensify this research in 1980. Because the Chinese hybrids and parental lines were not adapted to the tropics, IRRI began collaborating with several tropical rice-growing countries to develop suitable parental lines and hybrids. By 1989, IRRI developed two commercially usable cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines that, when combined with easily available restorers among elite tropical indica rice cultivars, produced hundreds of experimental rice hybrids. Some of these yielded about 1 t ha⁻¹ more than inbred checks in national trials under irrigated conditions. By 1994, India, Vietnam, and the Philippines had released some promising rice hybrids for commercial cultivation by farmers. New and better CMS lines are now available in the genetic background of irrigated, rainfed, boro, and